

Algorithms for Clustering and Visualizing High-Dimensional Points

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Abstract

This report presents a simple algorithm for points in 3D or higher-dimensional Euclidean space using overlapping spheres of fixed radius. The work was developed as part of an undergraduate independent study course (MAT 399) at DePaul University, supervised by Dr. Enrico Au-Yeung. Given a set of points, the goal is to group them into clusters where points in the same cluster are connected through chains of overlapping spheres, or to project high-dimensional data onto a 2D plane with reduced overlap between clusters. Algorithm 1 starts from an arbitrary point, iteratively expands the cluster by adding all points within a fixed distance d of any discovered point in the current cluster, and repeats the process for remaining points until all are assigned. Algorithm 2 is an improved version of Algorithm 1 that dynamically increases the search radius during cluster expansion when many new points are found (indicating higher local density), allowing it to better capture clusters with varying densities. Algorithm 3 is different from the previous two. This algorithm projects high-dimensional (e.g., 5D) points onto a 2D plane by starting with a random initial plane and gradually tilting/adjusting the projection plane (and its normal vector) as points are processed in order of closeness to the current base point.

1 Algorithm 1: Fixed-Radius Sphere-Based Clustering

This algorithm provides a simple method for grouping points in 3D space (or higher dimensions) using overlapping spheres of fixed radius d .

The core idea is to treat each point as the center of a sphere of radius d . Two points are considered connected if their spheres overlap or touch (i.e., their distance is at most $2d$). The algorithm identifies connected components where points are linked through chains of overlapping spheres.

The algorithm proceeds as follows:

- Randomly pick an uncovered point as the starting center and create an initial sphere of radius 1 around it.
- Find all remaining uncovered points that lie inside or on this sphere (distance ≤ 1 from the center) and add them to the current cluster.
- For each newly added point:
 - Create a new sphere of radius 1 centered at that point.
 - Check all still-uncovered points against the growing set of spheres: any point inside any sphere is added to the cluster.
- Repeat this process with the newly discovered points, effectively propagating through chains of overlapping spheres.
- Continue expanding until no more points can be reached (the cluster is complete).
- If uncovered points remain, randomly pick a new starting point from them and repeat the process to find the next cluster.
- Stop when all points are assigned to a cluster.

Pseudocode

```

1: procedure ALGORITHM 1(Points, d = 1.0)
2:   clusters  $\leftarrow$  empty list
3:   remaining  $\leftarrow$  set of all point indices  $\{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$ 
4:   while remaining is not empty do
5:     start_idx  $\leftarrow$  randomly select from remaining
6:     Cluster  $\leftarrow$  empty set
7:     Queue  $\leftarrow$  empty queue
8:     add start_idx to Cluster and Queue
9:     remove start_idx from remaining
10:    while Queue is not empty do
11:      current_idx  $\leftarrow$  dequeue from Queue
12:      for each idx in remaining do
13:        if distance(Points[current_idx], Points[idx])  $\leq 2 \times d$  then
14:          add idx to Cluster and Queue
15:          remove idx from remaining
16:        end if
17:      end for
18:    end while
19:    add sorted(Cluster) to clusters
20:  end while
21:  return clusters
22: end procedure

```

1.1 Simplified Implementation (Algorithm 1)

```
import random
import math

def distance(p1, p2):
    """Euclidean distance between two points."""
    return math.sqrt(sum((a - b) ** 2 for a, b in zip(p1,
        p2)))

def algorithm1(points, d=1.0):
    """
    Fixed-radius sphere-based clustering.

    Treats each point as the center of a sphere of radius
    d/2.
    Points are connected if their spheres overlap (distance
    <= d).
    Finds connected components using BFS-like propagation.
    """
    if not points:
        return []

    n = len(points)
    clusters = []
    remaining = set(range(n))

    while remaining:
        start = random.choice(list(remaining))
        cluster = {start}
        queue = [start]
        remaining.remove(start)

        while queue:
            new_batch = set()
            for curr in queue:
                for rem in remaining:
                    if distance(points[curr], points[rem])
                        <= d:
                        new_batch.add(rem)

            cluster.update(new_batch)
            remaining -= new_batch
            queue = list(new_batch)

        clusters.append(sorted(cluster))

    return clusters

# Example usage (uncomment to test)
```

```

"""
import numpy as np

np.random.seed(42)
cluster1 = np.random.normal(loc=[0, 0, 0], scale=1.0,
                             size=(300, 3))
cluster2 = np.random.normal(loc=[5, 5, 5], scale=1.0,
                             size=(200, 3))
points = np.vstack([cluster1, cluster2]).tolist()

clusters = algorithm1(points, d=2.0)
print(f"Found {len(clusters)} clusters with sizes: {[len(c)
for c in clusters]}")
"""

```


Figure 1: Results of Algorithm 1 on synthetic 3D data. Left: input points; right: clusters identified with fixed radius $d = 2.0$.

2 Algorithm 2: Adaptive Radius Clustering

This algorithm is an improved version of Algorithm 1. It groups points in 3D space (easily extendable to higher dimensions) using overlapping spheres, but introduces a **dynamic radius adjustment** that allows the search radius to grow slightly in dense regions of each cluster.

The key steps are as follows:

1. Randomly select an uncovered point as the starting center and initialize the sphere radius to d (default $d = 1.0$).
2. Find all remaining uncovered points within the current radius from any point already in the growing cluster and add them to the cluster.

3. After each expansion batch, compute the ratio of newly discovered points to the current cluster size.
4. If many new points are found (indicating high local density), increase the radius by $0.2 \times (\text{new points} / \text{current cluster size})$.
5. Cap the radius at $1.5 \times$ the initial d to prevent over-expansion.
6. Continue expanding with the updated radius until no more points can be reached.
7. If uncovered points remain, randomly pick a new starting point and repeat for the next cluster.
8. Stop when all points are assigned.

This adaptive mechanism allows the radius to grow gradually in dense areas for efficient capture, while remaining conservative in sparse regions.

Pseudocode

```
1: procedure ALGORITHM2(Points, initial_d = 1.0)
2:   clusters  $\leftarrow$  empty list
3:   remaining  $\leftarrow$  {0, 1, ..., n-1}
4:   while remaining  $\neq$   $\emptyset$  do
5:     start_idx  $\leftarrow$  randomly select from remaining
6:     Cluster  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
7:     Queue  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
8:     radius  $\leftarrow$  initial_d
9:     Add start_idx to Cluster and Queue
10:    Remove start_idx from remaining
11:    while Queue  $\neq$   $\emptyset$  do
12:      new_batch  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
13:      for each current_idx in Queue do
14:        for each idx in remaining do
15:          if distance(Points[current_idx], Points[idx])  $\leq$  radius then
16:            Add idx to new_batch
17:          end if
18:        end for
19:      end for
20:      if new_batch =  $\emptyset$  then
21:        break
22:      end if
23:      num_new  $\leftarrow$   $|\text{new\_batch}|$ 
24:      current_cluster_size  $\leftarrow$   $|\text{Cluster}|$ 
25:      radius  $\leftarrow$  initial_d + 0.2  $\times$  (num_new / current_cluster_size)
26:      radius  $\leftarrow$  min(initial_d  $\times$  1.5, radius)
27:      Add new_batch to Cluster and Queue
28:      Remove new_batch from remaining
29:    end while
30:    Append sorted(Cluster) to clusters
31:  end while
32:  return clusters
33: end procedure
```

2.1 Simplified Implementation (Algorithm 2)

```
import random
import math

def distance(p1, p2):
    """Euclidean distance between two points."""
    return math.sqrt(sum((a - b) ** 2 for a, b in zip(p1,
                                                       p2)))
```

```

def algorithm2(points, initial_d=1.0):
    """
    Adaptive radius sphere-based clustering.

    - Starts with initial_d
    - Increases radius in dense regions (up to 1.5 *
      initial_d)
    """
    if not points:
        return []

    n = len(points)
    clusters = []
    remaining = set(range(n))

    while remaining:
        start = random.choice(list(remaining))
        cluster = {start}
        queue = [start]
        remaining.remove(start)

        radius = initial_d

        while queue:
            new_batch = set()
            for curr in queue:
                for rem in remaining:
                    if distance(points[curr], points[rem])
                       <= radius:
                        new_batch.add(rem)

            if not new_batch:
                break

            num_new = len(new_batch)
            current_size = len(cluster)

            # Adaptive update: increase radius based on
            # density
            radius = initial_d + 0.2 * (num_new /
                                         current_size)
            radius = min(initial_d * 1.5, radius)

            # Update cluster and queue
            cluster.update(new_batch)
            remaining -= new_batch
            queue = list(new_batch)

        clusters.append(sorted(cluster))

```

```

        return clusters

# Example usage (uncomment to test)
"""
import numpy as np
np.random.seed(42)
cluster1 = np.random.normal(loc=[0, 0, 0], scale=1.0,
                             size=(300, 3))
cluster2 = np.random.normal(loc=[5, 5, 5], scale=1.0,
                             size=(200, 3))
points = np.vstack([cluster1, cluster2]).tolist()

clusters = algorithm2(points, initial_d=2.0)
print(f"Found {len(clusters)} clusters with sizes: {[len(c)
    for c in clusters]}")
"""

```


Figure 2: Results of Algorithm 2. The adaptive radius mechanism effectively captures clusters of similar densities.

3 Algorithm 3: Adaptive Plane Projection for High-Dimensional Points

Algorithm 3 is different from the previous two clustering algorithms. It is a projection method designed to map high-dimensional points (e.g., 5D) onto a 2D plane in a way that reduces overlap between clusters in the final view.

The core idea is to gradually tilt the projection plane as points are processed, attempting to find a viewing angle that better separates the clusters. The plane starts in a random orientation and slowly rotates toward directions that reveal new structural features.

The algorithm does the following steps:

- Pick three random points to create an initial plane: compute their average as the base point and derive a normal vector from the plane.
- Sort the remaining points by distance from the current base point (closest first) so that local points are processed together.
- For each point in that order:
 - Compute the direction vector from the current base point to the point.
 - Measure the angular difference from the current normal using $1 - |\cos \theta|$.
 - If the difference exceeds a threshold, update the normal by pulling it toward the new direction.
 - Move the base point to the current point.
 - Project the point onto the current plane using an orthonormal basis constructed from the normal (ensuring the 2D view always faces the normal directly).

This way, the projection plane gradually rotates to a viewpoint that aims to separate the clusters more effectively.

However, the algorithm has some limitations. Because the plane changes gradually as points are processed, points belonging to the first discovered cluster are mostly projected using planes close to the initial orientation. In contrast, points in later clusters are projected using more tilted planes. This path-dependent behavior can cause the clusters to still overlap in the final 2D view. Increasing the threshold reduces this overlap but makes the algorithm less sensitive to small directional changes.

3.1 Pseudocode

Require: Points $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, threshold τ , base weight w_b , max weight w_m

Ensure: 2D coordinates for all points

- 1: Randomly select three distinct points $p_1, p_2, p_3 \in P$
 - 2: $b \leftarrow \frac{p_1 + p_2 + p_3}{3}$ ▷ initial base point
 - 3: Compute initial normal n from p_1, p_2, p_3 (e.g., $(p_2 - p_1) \times (p_3 - p_1)$)
 - 4: $n \leftarrow n / \|n\|$ ▷ normalize
 - 5: Project p_1, p_2, p_3 onto the current plane to obtain their 2D coordinates
 - 6: Sort the remaining points by Euclidean distance to b (nearest first)
 - 7: **for** each remaining point p_i in sorted order **do**
 - 8: $d \leftarrow \frac{p_i - b}{\|p_i - b\|}$ ▷ direction vector
 - 9: $\text{diff} \leftarrow 1 - |n \cdot d|$
 - 10: **if** $\text{diff} > \tau$ **then**
 - 11: $\text{weight} \leftarrow w_b \times \text{diff}$
 - 12: $\text{weight} \leftarrow \min(\text{weight}, w_m)$
 - 13: $n \leftarrow n + \text{weight} \times d$
 - 14: $n \leftarrow n / \|n\|$ ▷ re-normalize
 - 15: $b \leftarrow p_i$ ▷ move base point
 - 16: **end if**
 - 17: Project p_i onto the current plane (using orthonormal basis from n) to get its 2D coordinates
 - 18: **end for**
 - 19: **return** all 2D coordinates
-

3.2 Simplified Implementation (Algorithm 3)

```
import numpy as np
import heapq

def project_to_2d(point, base_point, normal):
    """
    Project a point onto the plane defined by base_point
    and normal vector.
    Returns 2D coordinates (u, v).
    """
    projected = point - np.dot(point - base_point, normal)
        * normal

    # Construct orthonormal basis (u, v)
    arb = np.zeros_like(normal)
    arb[0] = 1.0
    if abs(np.dot(arb, normal)) > 0.99:
        arb[1] = 1.0
    u = arb - np.dot(arb, normal) * normal
```

```

u /= np.linalg.norm(u) + 1e-8

arb2 = np.zeros_like(normal)
arb2[2] = 1.0
v = arb2 - np.dot(arb2, normal) * normal - np.dot(arb2,
    u) * u
v /= np.linalg.norm(v) + 1e-8

x = np.dot(projected - base_point, u)
y = np.dot(projected - base_point, v)
return np.array([x, y])

def algorithm3(points, threshold=7.0, base_weight=5.0,
max_weight=15.0):
    """
    Incremental adaptive projection of high-dimensional
        points to 2D.

    - Starts with random initial plane
    - Processes points in order of distance from current
        base
    - Tilts normal vector when far points are encountered
    """
    points = np.array(points) # Ensure numpy array
    n, dim = points.shape

    # Initialize plane with 3 random points
    idx = np.random.choice(n, 3, replace=False)
    base_point = points[idx].mean(axis=0)

    v1 = points[idx[1]] - points[idx[0]]
    v2 = points[idx[2]] - points[idx[0]]
    v1 /= np.linalg.norm(v1) + 1e-8
    v2 /= np.linalg.norm(v2) + 1e-8

    arbitrary = np.zeros(dim)
    arbitrary[0] = 1.0
    normal = arbitrary - np.dot(arbitrary, v1) * v1 -
        np.dot(arbitrary, v2) * v2
    if np.linalg.norm(normal) < 1e-6:
        arbitrary[1] = 1.0
        normal = arbitrary - np.dot(arbitrary, v1) * v1 -
            np.dot(arbitrary, v2) * v2
    normal /= np.linalg.norm(normal) + 1e-8

    projected_2d = np.zeros((n, 2))
    for i in idx:
        projected_2d[i] = project_to_2d(points[i],
            base_point, normal)

```

```

# Priority queue: process nearest points first
pq = []
for i in range(n):
    if i not in idx:
        dist = np.linalg.norm(points[i] - base_point)
        heapq.heappush(pq, (dist, i))

while pq:
    _, i = heapq.heappop(pq)
    dist = np.linalg.norm(points[i] - base_point)

    if dist > threshold:
        direction = points[i] - base_point
        direction /= np.linalg.norm(direction) + 1e-8
        weight = base_weight * (dist / threshold)
        weight = min(weight, max_weight)
        normal += weight * direction
        normal /= np.linalg.norm(normal) + 1e-8
        base_point = points[i].copy()

    projected_2d[i] = project_to_2d(points[i],
                                   base_point, normal)

return projected_2d

# Example usage (uncomment to test)
"""
import numpy as np

np.random.seed(42)
cluster1 = np.random.normal(loc=(0, 0, 0, 0, 0), scale=1.0,
                             size=(300, 5))
cluster2 = np.random.normal(loc=(0.3, 0.3, 5.0, 0.1, 0),
                             scale=1.0, size=(200, 5))
points_5d = np.concatenate([cluster1, cluster2])

projected = algorithm3(points_5d, threshold=7.0,
                       base_weight=0)
print("Projection completed. Shape:", projected.shape)
"""

```


Figure 3: Projection results for Algorithm 3 on synthetic 5D data. Left: original X-Y view (heavy overlap); middle: X-Z view (clear separation); right: adaptive 2D projection produced by the algorithm.

4 Code Availability

Complete Python implementations that reproduce the figures are available at:
<https://github.com/joosung9956/sphere-clustering-projection>

References

1. Xin-She Yang. *Nature-Inspired Optimization Algorithms*. Elsevier, 2014.